

Impact of Atmospheric Boundary Profiling on Numerical Weather Prediction

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1 Introduction

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In this chapter we showcase the impact of (Atmospheric Boundary Layer) ABL profiling - mainly, but not exclusively through ground-based remote sensing - for applications in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP). Besides being proven to operate in a 24/7, unattended manner with suited QA and QC measures, national weather services need to be convinced of the actual benefit of ABL ground-based remote sensing in NWP. For this, we highlight some of the latest results in the areas of model evaluation and short-term forecasting with focus on the dynamic and thermodynamic structure of the ABL.

First, the value for **NWP model evaluation** is shown considering NWP model performance for thermally driven valley winds in complex terrain using a microwave radiometer and a Doppler lidar. Furthermore, the European ceilometer network is shown to provide important reference data for evaluating model forecasts of Saharan dust outbreaks. Second, we show the importance of ground-based remote sensing for **continuously deriving forecast indices**. In combination with satellite information, a hypothetical network of ground-based microwave radiometers could significantly improve spatial information on forecast indices potentially leading to improved warnings for convective storms. And finally, this chapter shows some of the latest impacts of ground-based remote sensing in **data assimilation for convection resolving NWP**. One-dimensional and three-dimensional Observations System Experiments (OSE) with Doppler lidars and microwave radiometers are discussed, as well as results from Observation System Simulations Experiments (OSSE), the later highlighting to different methodologies to quantify the impact of hypothetical ground-based remote sensing networks.

2 Model evaluation

2.1 NWP in complex topography

Contributors: Martine Collaud Coen, Maxime Hervo

Thermally driven valley winds and near-surface air temperature inversions are common over complex topography and affect the dynamics of air masses and pollutant concentration. The complex interactions that lead to the observed weather patterns are challenging for Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models. To study the performance of the COSMO-1E model analysis (KENDA-1), a measurement campaign took place from October 2021 to August 2022 in the 1.5 km wide Swiss Alpine valley called Haslital. A Microwave Radiometer (MWR) and a Doppler Wind Lidar were installed at Meiringen, in addition to several ground measurement stations recording meteorologic surface variables. The collected data shows frequent nighttime temperature (T) inversions for all months under study, which persist during daytime in colder months (Fig. 2.1.1). An extended thermal wind system was also observed during the campaign, except in December and January, allowing an extended analysis of along and cross valley winds.

The comparison between the observations and the KENDA-1 data provides good model performances for monthly temperature and wind medians but frequent and important differences for single profiles, especially in case of foehn events, leading to a near systematic underestimation of 2 to 4°C by KENDA-1 in both the ground and the profile temperatures. The frequency of occurrence and the amplitude of the surface T inversions are however both underestimated by KENDA-1 (see Fig. 2.1.1). This results in a systematic overestimation of the ground T (up to 8 °C) during the presence of surface-based inversions. This large model error has an important consequence, since the discrepancies between the model first guess prevents the SMN/MER observations to be assimilated.

Concerning the valley wind system, modelled flows are similar to the observations in their extent and strength. The vertical extent of the thermal winds, the onset time of down valley winds and the interaction with synoptic winds are also appropriately modelled. However, KENDA-1 shows a too early (1-2 hours) onset of up-valley winds due to the absence of the near surface stable layer caused by the nighttime inversion. The assimilation of the remote sensing observations could therefore improve the model performances regarding the ground T inversions and their implication in the thermal valley wind system.

Figure 2.1.1 a) Diurnal cycle of the hourly T inversion frequency between T at SMN/MER (589 m) and FEDRO/BRU (998 m) ground stations, at the lowest level (640 and 705 m, respectively) and 1000 m of MWR/MEE and KENDA-1/MEE profiles. The 1D measured values were interpolated using a linear interpolation with 10 m spaced vectors. b) Mean ΔT for the time where an inversion is detected. Sunrise and sunset are represented by dotted lines.

Further reading: Bugnard, A., Collaud Coen, M., Hervo, M., Leuenberger, D., Arpagaus, M., and Monhart, S.: Comparison between ground-based remote sensing observations and NWP model profiles in complex topography: the Meiringen campaign, EGU sphere [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-1961>, 2023.

2.2 Interplay between desert dust and meteorology

Contributors: Francesca Barnaba and Annachiara Bellini

Aerosols play a significant role in shaping the distribution of radiation in the atmosphere. In particular, an accurate description of the aerosol extinction vertical profiles in numerical, regional and global models is key to improve numerical simulations of chemical and physical processes taking place in the atmosphere, and in turn relevant products tailored to air quality, meteorology or climate studies. Among the different aerosol types loaded into the atmosphere, desert dust is one of the most important in terms of radiative impacts, being the most abundant in mass, and typically exhibiting a complex vertical stratification.

Remote sensing from both space and ground represents a powerful tool to describe and constrain the 4D spatiotemporal distribution of desert dust in the atmosphere, thus providing essential information to validate, and potentially drive through assimilation, NWP model simulations.

In a recent work by Rizza et al., (2023), the effects of mineral dust aerosols on radiation, meteorology and cloud properties (direct, semi-direct and indirect effects) were investigated through the Weather Research and Forecasting model coupled with Chemistry (WRF-Chem) over a domain covering Northern Africa and the Central Mediterranean basin. In this framework, the continuous data from ground-based automated lidar-ceilometer (ALC) systems operating across Italy were employed to quantitatively track the vertical and temporal evolution of a dust event (17-24 June 2021) and thus evaluate the ability of the model to correctly reproduce the mineral dust field within the spatial domain considered (see Fig. 2.2.1).

Figure 2.1.2 Left) Continuous time serie (17–24 June 2021) of the vertically resolved (0 – 6 km) aerosol extinction (at $1.064 \mu\text{m}$) as observed in 4 selected ALICENET ALC operating in (a) Milan, (b) Rome, (c) Messina and (d) Capo Granitola. Blank areas are those cloud screened. The Messina ALC data are missing from June 22 due to instrumental problems. Right) relevant simulations of the aerosol extinction coefficient at $0.55 \mu\text{m}$ (units km^{-1}) by WRF-Chem model. The inset map highlights location of the 4 selected ALICENET sites used in the study (Adapted from Rizza et al., 2023).

The ALC profiles revealed the first elevated desert dust plume to reach Italy on June 18, the southernmost site of Capo Granitola being the first one to detect it in the morning, followed by the others. The temporal shifts of the dust plume arrival at the different sites revealed the southwest to northeast movement of the air masses. The altitude range of this first plume is 3–5 km at all sites, and rapidly decreases below 3 km during the day. The second intense pulse was observed on July 19 and, similarly to the previous one, was firstly detected in the middle troposphere (4–5 km) and then observed to descend to the lowermost levels within the PBL in the following days, thus mixing with the first dust pulse as well as to local particles. A similar situation persists all over the country for two days, with further dust inputs arriving on 21 and 22 June and clearly affecting the lowermost layers (thus with potential implications on air quality), with the exception of the northernmost site of Milan. It is worth mentioning that a more advanced observation-based picture of similar dust transport

phenomena is expected to come in the next future exploiting the capabilities of polarisation-sensitive ALC systems (PLC) that are being progressively introduced within Alicenet (Bellini et al., 2024) and in Europe in general.

The model is shown to generally reproduce the observed pattern, although the magnitude of the dust plume on June 19 is slightly underestimated and aerosol loads tend to be overestimated closer to the dust source areas. As for the measurements, Milan is the less impacted site. The modelled Sahara dust layer is approximately 4 km depth for the whole period June 19–24. By performing a series of simulations adding and subtracting the aerosol field, it was possible to discriminate the role of aerosol-radiation and aerosol-microphysics feedback, and consequently the direct, semi-direct, and indirect impacts of mineral dust on radiation. These processes were shown to modify the dust radiative forcing and the energy budgets at the surface. Overall, this case study provided a clear show case of both the effects of dust aerosols on the atmospheric thermodynamic and radiative properties and of the utility of combining observations and models for such assessments.

Further reading: Rizza, U.; Avolio, E.; Morichetti, M.; Di Liberto, L.; Bellini, A.; Barnaba, F.; Virgili, S.; Passerini, G.; Mancinelli, E. On the Interplay between Desert Dust and Meteorology Based on WRF-Chem Simulations and Remote Sensing Observations in the Mediterranean Basin, *Remote Sens.* 2023, 15, 435, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15020435>

3 Forecast indices

3.1 Temporally highly resolved forecast indices

Contributors: Nico Cimini

Forecast indices (FI) have been developed since more than 60 years ago (REF) to relate atmospheric profiles measured by radiosondes to potential for high impact weather such as thunderstorm, fog, wind gusts. Several FI have been proposed in the past, most of which are based on similar thermodynamic approaches. The FI considered here include K index, total totals (TT), KO index, lifted index (LI), S index (SI), fog threat (FT), and convective available potential energy (CAPE). Although FI based on sounding observations are rather simple, they perform reasonably well, especially once optimised for site-specific conditions, and show forecast skills comparable with those of numerical weather prediction models. As such, FI are still broadly used in operational meteorology and local short-term forecasts.

Temperature and humidity profiles retrieved from ground-based instruments (e.g., MWR, IRS, DIAL) can be used to feed tools developed for processing radiosonde observations to obtain FI commonly used in operational meteorology. FI computed from ground-based remote sensing retrieved temperature and humidity profiles have been compared to those obtained from radiosondes, taken as a reference, showing different performances depending upon index and environmental situation. Overall, FIs computed from ground-based remote sensing retrievals agree well with radiosonde values, with correlation coefficients usually above 0.8, with the advantage (with respect to radiosondes) of nearly continuous updates.

Further reading: Cimini, D., Nelson, M., Güldner, J., and Ware, R.: Forecast indices from a ground-based microwave radiometer for operational meteorology, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 315–333, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-8-315-2015>, 2015

3.2 Ground-based and satellite synergy

Contributors: Maria Toporov and Ulrich Löhnert

Figure 3.2.1: Left three figures: RMSE of CAPE retrievals; Right three figures: RMSE of LI retrievals; RMSE fields are shown for $150 \times 150 \text{ km}^2$ domain in western Germany. The left plots of each figure group shows the RMSE values when only satellite observations are used as input, the middle plots using one additional ground-based MWR in the domain center, the right plots using 10 additional MWRs (corresponding to current SYNOP stations) to complement the satellite retrieval. The number in the right lower corner gives the averaged RMSE value for the shown domain.

The potential of complementing the future (launch planned for 2025) geostationary, hyperspectral Infrared Sounder (IRS) on board the Meteosat Third Generation Sounder Satellite (MTG-S) with a network of ground-based MWR to provide information on atmospheric stability is highly relevant for forecasting applications. Here, we consider a hypothetical ground-based MWR network over the western part of Germany to deliver the missing thermodynamic ABL information which the satellite cannot access.

In this experiment, atmospheric stability is described in terms of the forecast indices CAPE and Lifted Index (LI). Based on the COSMO-REA2 reanalysis as "truth", a neural network retrieval of CAPE and LI from simulated IRS and MWR measurements was developed (Toporov and Löhnert, 2021). Considering a single atmospheric column and clear sky conditions, both instruments, MWR and IRS, achieve almost similar accuracy with correlation values of 0.79 and 0.92 for CAPE and LI, respectively. Under cloudy conditions, MWR shows similar performance as under clear sky conditions, whereas the accuracy of IRS retrievals degrades leading to correlation values of 0.68 for CAPE and 0.79 for LI. The synergistic approach (i.e., using combined observations MWR+IRS as the input for neural networks) is beneficial under both, clear sky and cloudy conditions. The MWR+IRS retrieval is less sensitive to the presence of clouds and results in the correlation values of 0.88 and 0.97 for CAPE and LI, respectively.

To assess the spatial representativeness of observations of a single ground-based MWR and to investigate the impact of the MWR network in the presence of horizontally resolved IRS observations, the derived retrievals were applied to MWR and IRS observations simulated over the $150 \times 150 \text{ km}^2$ reanalysis domain covering the Rhein-Ruhr area. Using spatial statistical interpolation, the fields of CAPE/LI retrieved from IRS observations were merged with the CAPE/LI values from a network of MWR. The number of MWR distributed in the domain varied from 1 to 200. In the grid points with MWR, the synergistic retrieval (MWR+IRS) was applied to show the maximal possible impact. Within the statistical interpolation, the weight given to the CAPE/LI values in the grid points with available MWR observation is determined by the relationship between the error variance of both retrievals, IRS and MWR+IRS. The impact of MWR observations in the surrounding grid points is mostly determined by the error covariance matrix of IRS retrieval.

The left plots in Fig. 3.2.1 show the root mean squared error of the CAPE and LI fields retrieved from IRS observations. The middle and right column show the error of the fields obtained through the interpolation between the IRS retrieved fields and CAPE/LI values from a single MWR and from a network of 10 MWR. The results are shown for an all sky data set. Considering the clear sky and cloudy

cases separately, the decrease of the error and thus, the impact of additional ground-based MWR observations is more pronounced under cloudy conditions. One can add even more than 10 hypothetical MWRs. The decrease in the RMSE was shown to be significant for the first one to around 25 MWR distributed over the domain (corresponds to ~40 km distance between the instruments).

Further reading: Toporov, M., and U. Löhnert, 2021: Synergy of Satellite- and Ground-Based Observations for Continuous Monitoring of Atmospheric Stability, Liquid Water Path, and Integrated Water Vapor: Theoretical Evaluations Using Reanalysis and Neural Networks. *J. Appl. Meteor. Climatol.*, **59**, 1153–1170, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-19-0169.1>.

4 Data assimilation

4.1 Observation System Experiments (OSE)

4.1.1 Microwave radiometers (MWR) @ MeteoSwiss and DWD

Contributors: Jasmin Vural, Claire Merker, Moritz Löffler, Daniel Leuenberger, Christoph Schraff, Olaf Stiller, Annika Schomburg, Christine Knist, Alexander Haefele, Maxime Hervo

Over the last years, both DWD and MeteoSwiss investigated the direct assimilation of MWR brightness temperatures using a Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter (LETKF). Microwave radiometer data from Lindenberg (DWD), Payerne, and Grenchen (MeteoSwiss) were used for assimilation experiments using the KENDA data assimilation system with the ICON or COSMO model, respectively. The direct assimilation of measured brightness temperatures was implemented using RTTOV-gb (De Angelis et al. 2016, Cimini et al. 2019), which was developed in the TOPROF Cost Action, as observation operator.

Our results are published in Vural, Merker et. al. 2024 and outlined shortly in the following. Several assimilation experiments have been run comparing the assimilation of conventional observations only (CONV) with both CONV and MWR observations assimilated. Overall, we obtained mostly positive results in observation space; the results in model space are mostly neutral. It has proven difficult to translate the information contained in the brightness temperature observations into a positive impact on the model quality.

MeteoSwiss operationally integrated the MWRs in Payerne and Grenchen in its data assimilation system in summer 2022. The paper presents a representative analysis from a two-week period in spring 2023. The assignment of pressure level heights to the channels, which is needed for the localization in the LETKF, was analysed in preceding experiments. The vertical localization of the brightness temperature data is achieved by a combination of humidity, temperature, and cloud liquid water Jacobians to derive the pressure levels for each channel using a weighted average. The resulting pressure levels are mainly below 800hPa but are not completely constant with time. For some channels, the associated pressure levels show a strong sensibility to the state of the atmosphere (i.e., the presence of clouds). In addition to the vertical position of the data, the LETKF also required a so-called localization width which defines the vertical region in which the considered observation will influence the analysis. In the MeteoSwiss setup, this width is chosen to cover the whole vertical span of the model. With this setup, the vertical location of the impact of the MWR observations is only determined by the ensemble model error covariances of the background. The improvement of the brightness temperature representation in the model when assimilating MWR data is shown in Fig. 4.1.1.1, in which the standard deviation of the brightness temperature departures and residuals is clearly decreased. As mentioned, this improvement could not yet be transferred to the desirable impact on the model prognostic variables. Fig. 4.1.1.2 shows the neutral changes in the RMSE of the temperature and relative humidity first-guess departures for radiosounding observations in Payerne.

Figure 4.1.1.1: First guess (fg) and analysis (ana) departures in observation space for the MWR in Payerne, for the configuration with MWR assimilation (OPR; red lines) and the experiment without MWR assimilation (no MWR; blue lines). The left panel shows the mean and the right panel the standard deviation of the departures of the brightness temperatures of each assimilated channel. Note channels 1-7 are located in the K-band (water vapor and liquid water sensitive), channels 10-14 in the V-band (temperature sensitive).

Figure 4.1.1.2: First-guess departures for the sounding in Payerne, for the configuration with MWR assimilation (OPR) and the experiment without MWR assimilation (no MWR). The left panel shows the profile of the RMSE of the departures for the atmospheric temperature, the right panel that for the relative humidity.

Vural, Merker et. al. 2024 also present sensitivity studies for specific settings. At DWD, the impact of the vertical localisation and the number of assimilated channels was investigated systematically. As the cross-correlation of the observation errors cannot be taken into account properly by the assimilation system, a two-channel setup with channel 2 (ch2, located in the K-band and mainly water vapor and cloud liquid water sensitive) and channel 13 (ch13, located in the V-band and mainly temperature sensitive) was investigated further. It was found that, when assimilating both channels simultaneously, the height assignment (vertical localisation) of the single channels can be crucial. When comparing single channel experiments, the height assignment only had a secondary effect, though.

For the single-channel experiments, we assimilated ch2 for clear-sky and ch13 for all-sky conditions. The best ch13-only experiment (V1) yields a similar good impact as the best combined-channel (KV1) experiments (see upper air verification for MOL-RAO in Fig. 4.1.1.3), which can potentially be attributed to the larger number of observations assimilated due to the all-sky conditions. The results are often challenging to interpret due to the use of only one MWR and the lack of more frequent

verifying observations. Nevertheless, in total, a positive impact for both relative humidity and temperature was achieved in the NWP forecast for the ABL.

Figure 4.1.1.3: RMSE improvement (in %) for temperature T (top) and water vapor mixing ratio QV (bottom) for two assimilation experiments KV1 (left) and V1 (right), respectively, versus the reference run summarised over all lead times until 6 hr.

The number of MWR OSE experiments is expected to increase with the development of the MWR network within the EUMETNET E-PROFILE program (Rüfenacht et al. 2021) which began its operation in 2023.

Further reading: Vural, J., Merker, C., Löffler, M., et al. (2024) Improving the representation of the atmospheric boundary layer by direct assimilation of ground-based microwave radiometer observations. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 150(759), 1012–1028, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4634>

4.1.2 Microwave radiometers @ MeteoFrance

Contributors: Pauline Martinet, Guillaume Thomas, Pierre Brousseau, Philippe Chambon, Jean-François Georgis, Maxime Hervo, Thierry Huet, Ulrich Löhnert, Emiliano Orlandi, Vinciane Unger

Over the last years, Météo-France has investigated the benefit of the assimilation of MWR observations within the convective scale model AROME. Firstly using a simplified one-dimensional variational data assimilation system during several weather conditions (Martinet et al 2015, Martinet et al 2017, Martinet et al 2020). These studies have highlighted large errors of the AROME model in the ABL during stable conditions and during fog conditions. As a result the 1D assimilation of MWR is capable of reducing observation minus analysis differences compared to observation minus background differences.

In order to evaluate the capability of these systems in a real data assimilation framework taking into account all the other sources of observations already assimilated in AROME, a unique network of 8 ground-based microwave radiometers (MWR) has been deployed over the South-Western part of France in order to improve fog processes knowledge during the SOuth west FOGs 3D (SOFOG3D) experiment. This unprecedented deployment was possible thanks to the PROBE and TOPROF Cost Actions support. In order to assess the benefit of MWR observations, temperature profiles derived from MWR measurements at six different locations have been assimilated in the AROME model for a time period of three months with a three-dimensional variational assimilation system similar to the one used operationally in the AROME-France NWP model.

Firstly, positive impacts have been found on AROME-France 1 hour background and analysis, demonstrating that MWR observations can safely be integrated in the AROME assimilation system. Then, statistically significant positive impacts on temperature biases have been determined up to eight hours of forecast. Specific case studies have also proven that the assimilation of MWR observations could lead to the formation of fog when the initial configuration of the AROME model was unable to simulate the fog layer. A statistical evaluation of fog forecasts thanks to surface visibility measurements has also demonstrated an improvement in fog forecasts with a statistical significance up to 4 hours of forecast (Fig. 4.1.2.1).

These encouraging results pave the way for future studies in which a joint assimilation of temperature and humidity related variables could be considered or a direct assimilation of brightness temperatures.

These results are outlined in the publication under review: Thomas et al 2024, QJRMS, Assimilation of ground-based microwave radiometer temperature observations into a convective-scale NWP model for fog forecast improvement

Figure 4.1.2.1: Probability Of Detection (POD, upper left figures), Heidke Skill Score (HSS, lower left figures) Frequency Bias Index (FBI, upper right figures) and the False Alarm Ratio (FAR, lower right figures) for a visibility threshold of 500 m (left columns) and 1000 m (right columns) for the 24 hours of forecast lead time of the 133 forecasts ran for the 19 special observation periods. The red curve represents the REF experiment while the blue and green ones respectively represent the ALLOBS and THIN ones when MWR observations are assimilated. The dots on the curves represent statistically significant differences according to a Bootstrap test with a 95% confidence.

4.1.3 Radar wind profilers

The [E-PROFILE wind profiler network](#) has assessed the value of the wind observations from different types of radar wind profilers, wind from precipitation radars and airborne wind observations (AMDAR, Mode-S) for assimilation to global NWP (ECMWF) in an impact study by Rufenacht et al. 2018 based

on the Forecast Sensitivity to Observations Index (FSOI). They show the highest impact is achieved by troposphere-/stratosphere wind profilers.

4.1.4 Water vapor and temperature lidar

Contributors: Bas Crezee, Claire Merker, Maxime Hervo

Raman lidar (RL) and differential absorption lidar (DIAL) are two emerging active remote sensing technologies for water vapor and temperature profiling (Lange et al. 2019; Newsome et al. 2020; Weckwerth et al. 2016). While commercially available DIAL systems measure water vapor only (Gaffard et al. 2021), RLs combine the capability of temperature profiling and are therefore particularly interesting for assimilation experiments. With an integration time of typically 10 min, RL profiles cover the entire troposphere during nighttime and the lower troposphere (up to 4-5 km) during daytime. RL and DIAL cannot penetrate clouds and typically do not perform measurements during rain.

MeteoSwiss has performed a series of data assimilation (DA) experiments of temperature and humidity profiles (30 min availability) with its operational RL based in Payerne, Switzerland (Dinoyev et al. 2013, Brocard et al. 2013, Martucci et al. 2021). In a case study of a convective weather situation, Leuenberger et al. (2020) found that the 24h probabilistic precipitation forecast was improved when starting from an analysis including the assimilation of RL data as opposed to a reference setup corresponding to the operational setup at that time. The introduction of the operational assimilation of 2-m temperature and relative humidity observations in 2021 led to more constrained temperature and humidity fields. In a recent study in 2024, a more systematic assessment of the impact of RL assimilation was done covering two weeks in summer and two weeks in winter. A verification of the analysis against independent ground-based microwave radiometer data showed a reduction of 20-40% in the standard deviation of the moisture sensitive channels. In addition, in an experiment where the RL replaced the collocated radiosounding in the assimilation for the winter period, the analysis improved by 20-35%. This shows the potential for profiling instruments to add to analysis quality, especially in regions without a radiosounding. The impact to forecasts was found to be small.

4.1.5 Doppler lidar

Contributors: Maxime Hervo, Pirmin Kaufmann, Claire Merker, Daniel Regenass

Doppler Lidars are assimilated operationally in the COSMO Model at MeteoSwiss. In 2021, MeteoSwiss performed an experiment to evaluate the impact of an additional Doppler Lidar for numerical weather forecasts and dispersion calculation.

MeteoSwiss operates the COSMO model in combination with a data assimilation system composed of the following elements: COSMO-1E provides probabilistic forecasts using 10 ensemble members on a 1.1km grid up to +33h. The lateral boundary conditions are taken from the ECMWF global deterministic (IFS HRES) and ensemble (IFS ENS) models. The initial conditions for the COSMO-1E forecasts are produced with the Kilometric Ensemble Data Assimilation (Schraff, et al., 2016) system, based on a Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter (LETKF hereafter), which is running on the 1.1km grid.

The assimilation experiments yield a robust improvement for the analyses and the one hour lead time forecasts. This is in line with the findings from previous experiments with wind lidar instruments (Merker, Regenass, & Leuenberger, 2022) and with findings by the German weather service (Jasmin Vural, personal communication). In this study – and likely in general with standard verification metrics – the impact of the assimilation experiments during high impact cases is underestimated. Cases with strong winds show a positive impact of the assimilation experiment over up to seven hours lead time. The benefit of assimilating observations from wind profiler instruments may therefore be greater than the results our standard verification procedures suggest and thus also more relevant than previously assumed, e.g. in (Merker, Regenass and Leuenberger, 2022).

Figure 4.1.5.1: Dispersion of a constant release of 1 ton of air tracer over two hours at the Zeughausmatte site after 4 hours of model integration (release on April 6 2021 from 0 UTC to 3 UTC). Left: with the assimilation of Doppler Lidar. Right without the assimilation.

For dispersion calculation, the positive impact of the assimilation experiment may not be established directly due to the lack of verification data. From the case studies we can however infer that the improved analyses have a noticeable impact on dispersion modelling on the scale of 10 – 50 km during the first few hours (Fig. 4.1.5.1). As we have previously demonstrated an improvement for the wind fields for this lead time range in the assimilation experiments, it is reasonable to assume that the results in the assimilation experiment are more accurate. It is however unclear how significant this gain in accuracy is relative to the overall uncertainty of the dispersion modelling and how important this gain in accuracy is on smaller scales, which are more relevant to the cantonal authorities and the pharmaceutical industry. Nevertheless, it is clear that improved forecast skill will benefit dispersion modelling on all scales and the benefit should be quantified in a follow-up project.

4.1.6 Autonomous Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAV) or Systems (UAS)

FMI has operated an autonomous UAV system (multi-rotor copter equipped with dropsonde) for several months of a test period during summer and autumn months in consecutive years. In summary, the UAV technique is developing quickly and has become suitable for operational profiling the atmospheric boundary layer. Due to safety reasons and further regulations, human resources will be required for monitoring the autonomous operation. Observations can be gained with good accuracy (Laitinen, 2019). Weather forecasters use profile observations of meteorological variables in near-real time to supplement traditional radiosounding observations. These datasets have not yet been assimilated but are available for such studies.

With the same model set-up as described above, MeteoSwiss also conducted DA experiments assimilating profiles of temperature, humidity, and wind from UAV (Leuenberger et al. 2020). These experiments were focused on fog events, and it could be shown that the assimilation of temperature and humidity profiles significantly improves the analysis in terms of the presence / absence and distribution of fog. It is expected that the positive impact from the observations will last only for a few hours lead time. For better forecasts over longer lead times, also the model physics need to be improved.

PROBE has also been contributing to the WMO Uncrewed Aircraft Systems [\(UAS\) Demonstration Campaign](#) (UAS-DC) which aims at demonstrating the potential capability of UAS to play a role as an operational component of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS) under the Global Basic Observing Network (GBON). As an activity of the WMO Infrastructure Commission, WMO coordinates the holding of a UAS observations campaign, between March 2024 and August 2024. One major goal is to measure, analyse and report on the impacts of UAS observations on relevant WMO application areas and forecast systems.

4.2 Observation System Simulation Experiments (OSSE)

4.2.1 Ensemble variance reduction for wind energy applications

Contributors: Tanya Nomokonova and Ulrich Löhnert

An important question for wind energy applications is **how many ground-based Doppler wind lidars**, one of the core ABL network-capable instruments within PROBE, **are necessary to improve the short-term forecasts of low-level winds** over a specific target domain. Here, the Ensemble Sensitivity Analysis (ESA) approach is used. The ESA method allows to estimate the potential of the instruments before the observational network is built since this approach does not require real observations. The ESA approach was applied to a convective-scale 1000-member ensemble over Germany. Within this study the changes in the forecasted wind variance (uncertainty) assuming a hypothetical Doppler wind lidar network consisting of a different number of instruments observations have been investigated.

Figure 4.2.1.1: Distribution of the stations used for variance (uncertainty) reduction calculations. The blue dots correspond to the surface stations. The green dots indicate location of hypothetical wind lidar observations. Magenta dots denote the model the model grid used for the state vector. Figure adopted from Nomokonova et al., (2022)

Our study investigates the variance (uncertainty) reduction for the domain-averaged low-level wind speed at 80 m which is a typical hub-height of wind turbines. The forecasted low-level wind speed was averaged within the Rhein-Ruhr area (RRA, shown by grey rectangle in Fig. 4.2.1.1). The locations of the surface stations operationally used for assimilation by DWD are shown as well as the hypothetical wind lidar observations.

In our analysis the impact of a network of Doppler lidars was evaluated relative to the impact of surface observations. First, we estimated the variance reduction in the forecast metrics achieved from the surface stations located in and surrounding RRA (Fig. 4.2.1.1). At the next step, we calculated the variance reduction using the simulated data for the surface stations and a network of Doppler lidars. Locations of the hypothetical Doppler lidars were randomly chosen from the locations of surface stations. The experiments were performed for different combinations of the number of Doppler lidars in the network, the number of available range layers (from 80 m to 2.8 km) included in the Doppler lidar wind profiles, and the forecast lead time.

Fig. 4.2.1.2 summarises the changes in the variance reduction of the 3-hour forecast of horizontal wind components. Both wind components indicate a weak saturation effect and the divergence from the linear dependence starting at 20-30 wind lidars in the network for at least 3 levels in the wind profiles. The analysed cases indicate that on average 25 Doppler lidars give 3 times better variance reduction than surface stations only included in the network. Therefore, the most cost-efficient improvement of low-level wind in the RRA could be achieved by a network of ~25 Doppler lidars.

Figure 4.2.1.2: *Relative change in variance for different numbers of wind lidars in the network. The forecast metric is the u (a) and v-component (b) of the 80 m wind. Wind lidars observations are available at 1 (blue line), 3 (orange line), and 5 (green line) levels. The solid lines show the mean values over the 50 random locations sets of the wind lidars. The shadow areas denote 25th and 75th percentiles. Figure adopted from Nomokonova et al., (2022)*

The results show that a wind lidar network composed of 25 instruments bears high potential to significantly improve the low-level wind forecasts and that this impact is influenced by the ABL conditions (e.g. ABL height or cloud base height). More on this study is published in Nomokonova et al. (2022). In principle, the ESA methodology can be applied to arbitrary hypothetical observations relevant to renewable energy (or other) applications.

Further reading: Nomokonova, T., Griewank, P.J., Löhnert, U., Miyoshi, T., Necker, T. & Weissmann: Estimating the benefit of Doppler wind lidars for short-term low-level wind ensemble forecasts. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 1– 19, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4402>

4.2.2 Microwave radiometer OSSE in ICON domain

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To assess the impact of additional MWR observations in comparison to other operationally assimilated observations, a full OSSE was performed (in collaboration with Thomas Deppisch, DWD). A two-week Nature Run (NR) with corresponding operational and MWR observations was created using the OSSE tools of DWD. The advantage of the recently developed OSSE tools is the possibility to simulate all operational and MWR observations during the integration of NR. The assimilation experiments were performed over the ICON-D2 domain for two weeks (18 June to 06 July 2021) using the initial and boundary conditions from the ICON-EU model. To gain a realistic difference between the NR and Control Run (CR), the NR is initialised with a time lag of two days. The simulated observations were assimilated within an hourly cycle.

The MWRs were assumed to perform measurements in the grid points nearest to selected DWD surface stations (SYNOP) and E-PROFILE ceilometer stations (Fig. 4.2.2.1) resulting in 218 observational sites. The horizontal localization radius for MWR was set to 10 km. The assimilation experiments and CR were evaluated against the NR with an emphasis on the temperature and humidity profiles. The uncertainty of temperature and humidity profiles was calculated in the 218 grid points (not the entire domain).

Figure 4.2.2.1: *Experimental area of OSSE 2. Green stars and blue dots show the locations of MWR which are assumed to be collocated with currently operational radiosonde stations and stations with E-PROFILE ceilometers.*

The following experiments were performed:

- CONV: including SYNOP, AIREP, PILOT, DRIBU, TEMP observations,
- MWR: including only MWR observations,
- MWR+CONV: including CONV and MWR observations,
- CONV (w/o SYNOP): Including CONV observations without SYNOP,
- MWR+CONV (w/o SYNOP): including MWR and CONV without SYNOP observations.

Figure 4.2.2.2: RMSE of 1h-forecast (or first guess, solid lines) and the difference between the RMSE of the forecast and the subsequent analysis (dashed lines). Positive values indicate improvements due to assimilation. Left: Temperature. Right: specific humidity.

As can be seen in Fig. 4.2.2.2, conventional observations (CONV) improve the 1h-forecast (solid line) of the temperature only in the lowest 500m. The forecast of humidity is degraded compared to the CR. A positive impact on the analysis can be seen within the assimilation step (dashed lines) for both temperature and humidity but only in the lowest 500m. In the layers above the negative impact dominates. Moreover, the analysis profiles of specific humidity were shown to be physically inconsistent with strong fluctuations in adjacent levels (not shown here). Additional MWR observations (MWR+CONV) could improve the accuracy of the 1h-forecast of the humidity profiles in the layer between 500-5000m and slightly improve the impact of CONV within the assimilation step in the layers up to 1500 m for the temperature and from 500-4000m for humidity (dashed lines).

The exclusion of SYNOP observations from CONV experiments (CONV w/o SYNOP) leads to significant improvements in both temperature and humidity profile forecasts. The reason for the negative impact of SYNOP could be too large localization length of highly variable surface observations, which consequently have too strong an impact in the layers above.

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